

Keywords:

#AImodels, #energyforecasting,
#predictivemaintenance, #HVACindustry,
#EOOSCservices #machinelearning, #data-driven

Innovating HVAC Industry with AI Models: The PreMaCOOL Journey

Leveraging EOOSC Services for Energy Forecasting and Maintenance Solutions

The Project Involved

Klimamichaniki was founded in Thessaloniki, Greece in 1984. It is an engineering consultancy and construction company with expertise on all HVAC systems. The company recently pivoted towards research and development via incorporating and applying AI methods within its modus operandi, to develop innovative solutions.

<https://eosc-dih.eu/premacool/>

The Challenge

For interoperable data services, explicitly-defined data variables are crucial for usability, aligning with FAIR principles. Poorly-aligned semantic resources, though, complicate cross-disciplinary use. Despite progress, the terminology field faces new challenges like multilingualism, sustainable concepts, and reuse. Unified strategies are needed for vocabulary definition across research areas. Challenges include completeness variations, monolithic frameworks, and limited curation. Software designs for semantic artifacts must tackle data quality requirements

The Research Community

We are a commercial company in engineering and constructing, recently we are also into research and development via incorporating and applying AI methods within its modus operandi, to develop innovative solutions.

Thanasis Anagnostis

Research, Development and Innovation Manager at Klimamichaniki

“The development of AI models for energy forecasting and predictive maintenance is innovative for the specific domain, enabling Klimamichaniki to gain new knowledge during the EOOSC DIH pilot and eventually develop innovative complementary services for industrial installations.”

EOOSC service or tool used

- OpenAIRE EXPLORE: Academic research - OpenAIRE NEXUS <https://explore.openaire.eu/>
- EGI Notebook: Develop code - EGI Foundation (EGI-ACE) <https://www.egi.eu/service/notebooks/>
- DEEP training facility: Train models - <https://deep-hybrid-datacloud.eu/the-platform/>
- ARGOS: Create data management plan - OpenAIRE NEXUS <https://argos.openaire.eu/splash/>
- B2SHARE: Networking and dissemination of results - EUDat (DICE Project) <https://www.eudat.eu/catalogue/b2share>

PreMaCOOL has a sequential implementation plan, common in most research works, study the bibliography and market, try the solution in mind, adhere to any obligations and restrictions and finally share the results. Therefore the logical way to implement EOOSC services was to utilize OpenAIRE EXPLORE for academic research, and use search engines to search for similar existing solutions. Then, access to tools and resources were required to develop code, implement ideas, train models, and test their results., therefore EGI Notebook and Deep Training facility were a perfect fit. In fact, most of the PreMaCOOL effort was spent using these two services. Then, PreMaCOOL utilized ARGOS to create a data management plan, which is necessary since the data that were used were not public therefore a data management plan might come useful in the future. Finally, B2SHARE was selected to disseminate the results of PreMaCOOL. This has not been used yet, however, it is within the plan.

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Useful tips & tricks

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Benefits and impact

Within PreMaCOOL, Klimamichaniki has accomplished a set of achievements:

- Developed a set of anomaly detection models based on point-wise (One-class SVM, Local Outlier Factor, Isolation Forest, Autoencoders) and pattern-wise (Hidden Markov Models, LSTM autoencoders, CNN autoencoders) detection mechanism. Visual inspection on the data showed accurate detection of present anomalies.
- Developed a set of energy forecasting models with hourly granularity and forecasting depth of 24 hours, aiming to predict next day's consumption patterns. The selected algorithms (SARIMA, LSTM, Transformers, Neural Prophet) managed to achieve mean square errors below 0.01.
- Through the engagement with the pilot and EOSC DIH, two new ideas were conceptualized on innovative solutions based on data and AI methodologies. One of them has been submitted for funding via the funding calls proposed by EOSC DIH.
- The competence of HVAC engineers, towards identifying potential data-driven solutions to existing market problems, has been significantly increased. The company's engineers are now in a continuous engagement and discussions on whether implementation of data-driven AI solutions could potentially address a number of specific problems in the domain.

Useful material related to this story

eosc-dih.eu/premacool/

Why do I need EOSC?

EOSC provided the services and infrastructure that was crucial for Klimamichaniki to proceed with the creating of a strategy and the training AI models at this stage of development. Since the company is not a software company and has only recently started being involved in innovation concepts, EOSC provided with the tools and the human support to guide us through this endeavour.

Across disciplines

Development of machine learning models is not an easy task for non-experts. Klimamichaniki has vast experience in the energy and HVAC domain, but is new to implementing machine learning and artificial intelligence algorithms. We hope our experiences will be valuable for the R&D departments of other SME's and start-ups who want to start with AI and ML.

Limitations and future improvement

Given that PreMaCOOL has reached a satisfactory point and some promising results have been produced, two services that could be useful at this stage (but I'm not sure if they were available at the time of submission), are:

- production-level software and operations: a set of tools and experts that could enable the SMEs to bring their early-stage solution and make it a production-level product with software engineering techniques and DevOps. Especially for AI and ML project, which is very common lately, MLOps and deployment would be also included.
- business consultancy: a set of experts that would create potential business ideas from the developed product, and help the SME to select the best one based on the potential and the market. This would also include exploitation plans and possibly scale-up possibilities.

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